

Examining the climate change impacts on floral diversity in Bangladesh: The way of Forest Mensuration

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Abstract

The overall objective of the study was to examine the impact of climate change on floral diversity through forest mensuration. Only secondary data were used in this study. Inventory data can be integrated with environmental and climatic information to understand the drivers of forest stand dynamics under a changing climate in Bangladesh, where long-term forest data series are absent. Establishing circular plots at the core areas of each conservation can provide sufficient data to understand the natural dynamics. Calculation of biodiversity indices like Species richness, Similarity index, Importance Value Index, Shannon-Wiener Index, Simpson Index, the evenness and Disturbance Index can be effectively used to understand the drivers of forest stand dynamics under a changing climate and anthropogenic disturbances.

Keywords: Changing climate, floral diversity, conservation sites, circular plots, biodiversity indices

Introduction

Forest Mensuration provides forest inventory, forest resource monitoring, measurement principles, stand structure parameters, different sampling methods and applications. It takes into account all the resources of a forest, including timber and non-timber vegetation parameters, natural regeneration, lesser vegetation, coarse woody debris, and carbon flux (Matthews and Mackie 2006). A deeper understanding of natural forest dynamics requires long-term data series from forests that have not been affected by human interventions, which are absent in Bangladesh. Degraded, but regularly inventoried natural forest provides an opportunity to fill this gap (Szegeti *et al.* 2023). The individual tree history indicates human disturbances, regeneration ingrowth, growing phase, mortality, decaying phase and disappearance events, that can be used for the calculation of natural dynamics. The dataset can the changes in stand structures and tree population dynamics. Inventory data can be integrated with environmental and climatic information to understand the drivers of forest stand dynamics under a changing climate (Szegeti *et al.* 2023).

Forest Mensuration for examining the impact of climate change in Bangladesh

Establishing permanent mensuration plots

A permanent mensuration sample plot provides the databank of the individual tree. It manages the network of permanent and temporary sample plots representing a wide range of species, sites, yield classes and management practices. The sample plots provide the basic information (data and analysis), and necessary information for planning, and policy formulations including those related to climate change, inventory and production forecasting purposes. Establishing 300 m² (radius = 9.77m) circular plots at the core areas of each conservation site is considered suitable experimental plots in forest inventories in Bangladesh (Rahman *et al.* 2007, 2008, 2009, 2010, Rahman 2009, 2020; Rahman and Vacik 2009, 2010). The full sample plot will be considered for the data investigation of the mature trees (>10cm dbh), coarse woody debris (>5cm dbh and >1.37m height), saplings and climbers. Within the 300m², a subplot of 100m² area (r=5.64m) will be considered for the inventory of established seedlings and another subplot of 12.6m² area (r=2m) for ephemerals. The distance between two adjacent plots will be 100m in any direction. The number of plots will be determined by the equilibrium condition of species-area curves. Each plot will be divided into several sub-plots for measuring different parameters.

Criteria for selecting mensuration sites

- * Core areas
- * Presence of minimum anthropogenic disturbances
- * Mixed forest
- * Natural-semi natural forest
- * High species richness
- * Heterogeneous forests
- * Presence of natural regeneration
- * Highly diversified forests (diversity in species composition; horizontal and vertical structure; vital, social and age classes)
- * Presence of ground vegetation (shrubs, herbs and climbers)
- * Presence of indicator, keystone, umbrella, flagship, rare and endangered species

Mensuration sites

Considering the above criteria, the core areas of the following conservation sites can be selected as mensuration sites (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Way of sampling

Figure 2: A sample plot

S.N.	Name	Location
1	Bhawal National Park	Gazipur
2	Modhupur National Park	Tangail/Mymensingh
3	Ramsagar National Park	Dinajpur
4	Himchari National Park	Cox' Bazar
5	Lawachara National Park	Moulavibazar
6	Kaptai National Park	Chittagong Hill Tracts
7	Nijhum Dweep National Park	Noakhali
8	Medha Kassapia National Park	Cox's Bazar
9	Satchari National Park	Hobigonj
10	Rema-Kelenga Wildlife Sanctuary	Hobigonj
11	Char Kukri-Mukri Wildlife Sanctuary	Bhola
12	Sundarban (East) Wildlife Sanctuary	Bagerhat
13	Sundarban (West) Wildlife Sanctuary	Satkhira
14	Sundarban (South) Wildlife Sanctuary	Khulna
15	Pablakhali Wildlife Sanctuary	Chittagong Hill Tracts
16	Chunati Wildlife Sanctuary	Chittagong
17	Teknaf Game Reserve	Cox's Bazar
18	National Botanical Garden	Dhaka
19	Madhabkunda Eco-Park	Moulavibazar
20	Sitakunda Eco-park	Chittagong

Figure 1: The proposed mensuration sites and the way of sampling

Duration

Data on the following parameters will be collected at the 10-year interval for 50 years to predict the impacts of climate change on floral diversity. It is noteworthy to mention that a major portion of the change will be occurred through anthropogenic disturbances. Considering

the level of protection and disturbance index it will be possible to assess the climate change impacts.

Parameters

- * Number of species to measure the change in species richness and species composition
- * Diameter at breast height, height, crown length, and trunk height of each mature tree to measure the temporal carbon flux
- * Crown classes of trees (dominant, co-dominant, intermediate and suppressed tree) to measure the change in social class distribution
- * Vital classes (high, medium, low and poor) of trees to assess the change in tree vitality
- * Number of saplings, established seedlings, ephemeral for each tree species to measure the change in natural regeneration pattern, natural succession and potentiality of early successional species
- * Diameter and height/length of standing and lying of dead wood to measure the temporal mortality
- * Number of species-wise shrubs and climbers, and the approximate proportion of each herb species to measure the change in ground vegetation
- * Positioning of trees to measure the changes in clumping pattern\
- * Abundance and species richness of alien invasive species to assess the trend of colonization

Biodiversity indices

Species richness: The species richness will determine the sensitivity of each ecosystem and its resident species.

Similarity index (community coefficient): The similarity index will help to find out the trend of species overlapping

Importance Value Index (IVI): The Importance Value Index will assess the change in the structural role and dominance of each species based on relative frequency, abundance and dominance.

Shannon-Wiener Index (diversity index): The diversity index will measure the changes in species diversity and community composition.

Simpson Index (the concentration of dominance): The concentration of dominance will determine the change in the distribution pattern of different species.

The evenness: Evenness will measure the relative abundance of different species making up the richness of an area.

Disturbance Index: This will assess the trend of human disturbances. The intensity of each disturbance element will be categorized based on qualitative assessment. Each category will be weighted.

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